

Amperometric Titrations by A. C. Polarography

S. L. Gupta and S. K. Sharma

It is shown that amperometric titrations in dilute solutions and the composition of the precipitate formed can be successfully investigated by a. c. polarography with an accuracy of $\pm 1.0\%$.

Much work has been done on various types of amperometric titrations using conventional polarography, but no data are available in literature on such studies by a. c. polarography. The purpose of the present investigation is therefore to ascertain if a. c. polarography can be advantageously applied for such estimations in dilute solutions as well as to investigate the composition of the precipitates formed. For this purpose, the results obtained in the amperometric titrations of nickel with ferrocyanide as well as lead with oxalate and with dichromate, using a. c. polarography, have been discussed.

EXPERIMENTAL

Pure recrystallised nickel sulphate ($\text{NiSO}_4 \cdot 6\text{H}_2\text{O}$), lead nitrate, potassium dichromate, potassium oxalate, and potassium ferrocyanide (B. D. H., A.R.) were used. Mercury used for the dropping electrode was purified by passing it through Meyer's column after which it was washed several times with distilled water, dried, passed through a sintered glass filter, and finally distilled under vacuum.

The technique of a. c. polarographic measurement was the same as that described by Doss *et al.*¹ earlier, the only modification being that the series resistance was made as small as possible, which was achieved by introducing suitable resistances in the a. c. ripple circuit and minimising the resistance across which the a. c. ripple was obtained. This consisted in applying to the d.m.e. a 50 c/sec. a. c. ripple of 20 mV (r.m.s.) on the d.c. potentials and observing the alternating component of the resulting pulsating current.

0.1M-KCl (B.D.H., A.R.) solution in conductivity water was used as the supporting electrolyte for the titration of nickel with ferrocyanide, whereas 0.1 M-KNO₃ (B. D. H., A.R.) solution was used for the titration of lead oxalate and dichromate. Negative d.c. potentials were applied to the d.m.e. with respect to the saturated calomel electrode. The experiments were carried out at a constant temperature of $30^\circ \pm 0.5^\circ$. The constants of the d.m.e. were: '*m*' = 4.564 mg./sec. and '*t*' = 1.8 sec. per drop in 0.1 M-KCl, open circuit. The titrations between nickel and ferrocyanide were carried out at a potential of -1.08 volt vs. S.C.E., whereas -0.52 volt vs. S.C.E. was used for lead oxalate and lead

dichromate titrations. At these potentials nickel and lead produced very high a.c. peaks respectively, whereas potassium ferrocyanide, potassium oxalate, and potassium dichromate were not reduced at the d.m.e. at above potentials.

A typical curve depicting the results of titration of $2.5 \times 10^{-3} M$ solution of nickel

FIG. 1

sulphate with $5.0 \times 10^{-3} M$ potassium ferrocyanide solution is shown in Fig. 1. Table I records the various titration results obtained at pH 2.1. Similar titration results were also obtained at pH 6.8. Saraswat and Agarwal² investigated the composition of nickel ferrocyanide, following the amperometric titration of Ni^{2+} from 1.25 to 40 mM concentration against potassium ferrocyanide, using conventional polarography, and showed the composition as $3 NiK_2[Fe(CN)_6]$, $Ni_2[Fe(CN)_6]$ or $Ni_3K_6[Fe(CN)_6]$. From our titration relationship, the composition of the precipitate formed appears to be essentially $Ni_3K_6[Fe(CN)_6]$ over the entire range of strength of ferrocyanide used.

The results obtained for various titrations of lead with oxalate and lead with dichromate are shown in Tables II and III respectively. The composition of the precipitates formed appears to be essentially PbC_2O_4 , and $PbCrO_4$ respectively, which agree with the composition of the precipitates obtained using conventional polarography^{3,4}.

TABLE I

Nickel with potassium ferrocyanide.

$NiSO_4$ soln. = 50.0 ml. pH = 2.1. Supporting electrolyte = 0.1M-KCl.
 $E_s = 1.08V$ vs. S. C. E.

Concentration (mole/litre)		Titre values.		%Error.
$NiSO_4$.	$K_4Fe(CN)_6$.	Calc.	Obs.	
1.25×10^{-3}	5.00×10^{-3}	1.00 ml	1.01ml	+1.0
1.50×10^{-3}	5.00×10^{-3}	1.28	1.28	0.0
2.50×10^{-3}	5.00×10^{-3}	2.00	2.00	0.0
3.15×10^{-3}	1.00×10^{-2}	1.28	1.26	0.0
5.00×10^{-3}	1.00×10^{-2}	2.00	2.01	+0.5
5.00×10^{-3}	1.25×10^{-2}	1.60	1.58	-1.0
1.00×10^{-2}	1.00×10^{-2}	4.00	4.00	0.0
5.00×10^{-3}	1.00×10^{-2}	2.00	2.00	0.0
2.00×10^{-2}	4.00×10^{-3}	2.00	2.01	+0.5

2. Proc. Ind. Acad. Sci., 1957, 45A, 91.

3. Kolthoff and Lingane, "Polarography", Vol II, Interscience Publishers, Inc., New York, 1952, p. 690.

4. Kolthoff and Fan, J. Amer. Chem. Soc., 1930, 51, 3403.

TABLE II

Lead with potassium oxalate.

Pb(NO₃)₂ soln. = 50.0 ml. pH = 5.6. Supporting electrolyte = 0.1M-KNO₃.
*E*_s = -0.52V vs. S.C.E.

Concentration. (mole/litre)		Titre values.		%Error.
Pb(NO ₃) ₂ .	K ₂ C ₂ O ₄ .	Calc.	Obs.	
1.0 × 10 ⁻²	1.0 × 10 ⁻¹	5.0 ml	5.00 ml	0.0
1.5 × 10 ⁻³	1.5 × 10 ⁻²	5.0	5.00	0.0
1.0 × 10 ⁻³	1.0 × 10 ⁻²	5.0	5.00	0.0
7.5 × 10 ⁻⁴	7.5 × 10 ⁻³	5.0	5.00	0.0
5.0 × 10 ⁻⁴	5.0 × 10 ⁻³	5.0	4.97	-0.6
2.5 × 10 ⁻⁴	2.5 × 10 ⁻³	5.0	4.49	-1.2

TABLE III

Lead with potassium dichromate.

Pb(NO₃)₂ soln. = 50.0 ml. pH = 6.8. Supporting electrolyte = 0.1M-KNO₃.
*E*_s = -0.52V vs. S.C.E.

Concentration. (mole/litre)		Titre values.		% Error.
Pb(NO ₃) ₂ .	K ₂ Cr ₂ O ₇ .	Calc.	Obs.	
1.0 × 10 ⁻²	5.00 × 10 ⁻²	5.0 ml	5.05 ml	+1.0
1.0 × 10 ⁻³	5.00 × 10 ⁻³	5.0	5.00	0.0
5.0 × 10 ⁻⁴	2.50 × 10 ⁻³	5.0	5.00	0.0
7.5 × 10 ⁻⁵	3.75 × 10 ⁻⁴	5.0	5.00	0.0
5.0 × 10 ⁻⁵	2.50 × 10 ⁻⁴	5.0	4.97	-0.6

A clear and distinct end point could be observed in the titrations of even diluted solutions, viz., 2.0 × 10⁻⁴M of Ni²⁺ with ferrocyanide; 2.5 × 10⁻⁴M of Pb²⁺ with oxalate; 5.0 × 10⁻³M of Pb²⁺ with dichromate, by this technique, but this is not possible by the amperometric titrations using conventional polarographic method. These estimations can be made with an accuracy of ±1.0%. It is therefore concluded that amperometric titrations in dilute solutions and the composition of the precipitates formed can be successfully investigated by using a. c. polarography.

Thanks are due to the Director and Head of the Department of Chemistry, Birla Institute of Technology and Science, Pilani, for providing facilities and to the C.S.I.R., New Delhi, for the award of a research fellowship to one of them (S.K.S.).